

D3.3 - Stakeholder Engagement and Onboarding

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BUILD

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1 Introduction

This report serves as a comprehensive overview of the engagement and commitment levels of the stakeholders previously identified and mapped within the BUILD project activities. The assessment of stakeholder engagement and commitment has been conducted through a collaborative online survey, thoroughly reviewed by all project partners.

Specifically, this document focuses on evaluating stakeholder interest and commitment within the context of Work Package 4 (WP4) activities, which encompass elements such as trainings, staff exchanges, and newsletters. The primary objective of this assessment is to gain insights into stakeholder interest in these activities and gauge their commitment to active participation. The findings from this evaluation will inform the refinement of our strategies and offerings to better align with stakeholder needs, thereby ensuring the success of WP4 activities within the innovation ecosystem we aim to foster.

This report is structured in a logical and user-friendly manner to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the stakeholder engagement and commitment assessment. It is divided into several sections, including Methodology, Survey Results, Implications and next steps, and Annexes. Each section contributes to providing a holistic view of our assessment process, findings, and actionable insights for enhancing stakeholder engagement within the BUILD project.

2 Methodology and concept

This chapter is designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the processes and strategies we have employed to gather, analyse, and interpret data accurately and effectively.

2.1 Engagement concept to gauge Stakeholder Interest and Commitment

Effective capacity-building activities rely on precise and strategic stakeholder engagement. The BUILD consortium has invested significant time and effort in ensuring that engagement is carried out thoughtfully. Our approach, depicted in Figure 1, is grounded in three key tasks: Value Proposition, Mapping & Scouting, and Engagement and Onboarding.

The BUILD approach is a two-step process. First, it consists of “onboarding” as a passive method to get important stakeholders involved in our activities, by scouting and mapping them. The second step involves an active engagement of important stakeholders directly using a warm approach based on direct emails and a survey. Combined, this ensures a filled funnel with different levels of commitment and engagement supported by Social Media promo posts. The Social Media posts highlighted the importance of innovation procurement in cities, and briefly explained the topics and goals of the trainings. All the BUILD Social Media channels were used, including Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter. PEDAL also used its account and professional network to disseminate further the survey and the activity of the trainings.

Figure 1 BUILD approach for stakeholder engagement

This report specifically focuses on Task T3.3, which pertains to the initial engagement of the stakeholders identified and scouted during the earlier phases of our project, specifically in Task 2.3 This crucial step precedes full-scale engagement for the specific actions outlined in Work Package 4 (WP4). The purpose of this preliminary engagement is to ensure that our outreach efforts are directed toward individuals and entities genuinely interested in our activities. It serves as an essential safety measure, enabling the consortium to adapt if engagement levels are lower than anticipated. Additionally, it helps prevent unnecessary communication, ensuring that our interactions are relevant and purposeful.

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2.2 Target Audience: Mapped Stakeholders

Understanding the identity of our survey respondents is paramount. In this section, we provide insights into the selection and identification of the target audience, particularly focusing on stakeholders identified in the mapping and scouting exercise. These include: “innovation demand”, “innovation supply”, “multipliers + others”, and “projects”.

For all stakeholder types, the following information was systematically collected:

- Organization Name
- Website
- Geographical Information
- Contacts in compliance with GDPR.
- Collaboration History

Stakeholder Category	Definition	Cluster Criteria
Innovation Demand	Entities or individuals from the public and private sectors seeking innovative products, services, or solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation Demand Type: Individual Public Buyer, Central Purchasing Body, Regional Purchasing Body, Private Purchasing Body (not direct target), Other. • Level of Activity: City level, Regional, Transregional, National, EU, International, N/A. • NUTS 2021 Classification: NUTS 1, NUTS 2, NUTS 3. • Estimated Yearly Budget: Small (Up to 10% of the annual budget), Medium (Up to 25% of the annual budget), Large (More than 25% of the annual budget).
Innovation Supply	Key players in the innovation ecosystem contributing to the development and supply of innovative products, services, or solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Field of Innovation Relevant for BUILD: Green Mobility, Bioeconomy, Circular Economy, Education, Company Training.
Multipliers	Various stakeholders facilitating and supporting innovation activities, including intermediaries, lobbies, associations, advisors, and policy makers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiplier Stakeholder Type: Intermediary, National Center for Public Administration Training, Industrial Cluster, Investor/Alternative Financing, Associations/Lobby, Advisors/Consultancy/Legal, Policy Maker, Trade Union/Civil Society, European Institution, Media, Other. • Level of Activity: City level, Regional, Transregional, National, International, EU, N/A.
Projects	Specific initiatives or endeavours focused on innovation procurement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State: Ongoing, Concluded. • Area: Innovation Procurement, Health, Climate Change, Circular Economy. • Domain: Public Procurement of Innovation (PPI), Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP), Public Procurement (PP), Green Public Procurement (GPP), Sustainable Public Procurement (SPP). • Programme, Start and End Date, Coordinator, Coordinator Country. • Projects Assets and Links: Reports, Tools, Events to be exploited.

2.3 Stakeholders Survey Participation

The survey encountered a positive and expected number of participants which allows the consortium to fulfil its duties optimally. In total, the survey received 19 answers, distributed among the previously identified stakeholders' groups as detailed in the pie chart on Figure 2. This is a high amount of interested stakeholders considering the stage of the BUILD activities.

Sample distribution of stakeholders

Figure 2 Distribution of survey responses according to stakeholder group

2.4 Survey Design: Question Types, Structure, and Content

In this section, the consortium will provide an overview of the survey's structure. This will include the types of questions used, how the survey was organized, and the topics covered to assess stakeholder interest and commitment.

The survey was deliberately designed to be concise and user-friendly, with the aim of respecting the stakeholders' time. It begins with a brief introduction, explaining why stakeholders were asked to participate and providing essential information about the BUILD project and the consortium partners.

Following the introduction, stakeholders are invited to identify their respective organizations. The survey then uses a straightforward checkbox format with multiple columns for questions. Stakeholders can indicate their level of interest or commitment by selecting options for each planned activity, such as:

1. I would like to stop being informed about this action
2. I would like to remain informed about this action
3. I would be interested in participating in this action

This survey design ensures an efficient and effortless experience for our stakeholders, without causing unnecessary disruption to their schedules.

2.5 Data Analysis Techniques

The process of transforming raw survey data into meaningful insights is articulated in this section. A descriptive analysis was conducted to provide a summary of key survey metrics. This included the distribution of responses across different stakeholder categories and the overall engagement levels observed. This enables the consortium to tailor BUILD activities to align with the expressed interests and commitments of diverse stakeholders. This approach ensures that the project remains responsive to stakeholder needs and fosters meaningful engagement throughout its lifecycle.

3 Survey Results

The findings suggest a positive level of commitment from respondents, indicating a strong interest in staying informed and actively contributing in BUILD activities. At this stage, where the concept behind the trainings have not fully matured, this is a luxury position to be in. These insights will be instrumental in tailoring future activities to better align with stakeholder expectations and maximize engagement in the BUILD project.

The survey assessed stakeholder interest in the WP4 trainings, and the results indicate varying levels of engagement across the three training sessions. The engagement in WP4 training activities is high, but slightly diminishes over the different trainings over time:

- *Training Session 1:* Showed the highest participation rate, suggesting a strong initial interest or relevance to stakeholders.
- *Training Session 2:* Followed with a slightly lower participation rate, indicating sustained interest but with a potential decrease.
- *Training Session 3:* Exhibited the lowest participation rate, suggesting a diminishing interest or a shift in stakeholder priorities.

4 Implications and Next Steps

The initial survey results mark a significant step in our commitment to stakeholder engagement within the BUILD project. These findings underscore the importance of actively seeking and thoroughly analysing stakeholder feedback for continuous improvement. A recommended approach is to iterate on the planning and execution of WP4 activities, using insights from stakeholder input to optimize future initiatives. To engage even more stakeholders, there exists a need for targeted communication strategies, prompting efforts to refine outreach methods. Clearly articulating the value proposition of BUILD activities is vital for ensuring sustained and meaningful stakeholder involvement. It is important to note that the BUILD consortium will continue to engage with ALL scouted and mapped stakeholders. The ensuing implications and recommendations chapter will outline a strategic path forward, demonstrating our commitment to enhancing stakeholder engagement through a responsive and adaptive project framework.

Collect additional feedback for session two and three

Firstly, the observed differences in participation rates across training sessions highlight the need for a nuanced approach in aligning session content with the evolving priorities of stakeholders. Alternatively, the decrease in participation numbers can be explained by the fact that the level of required commitment to attend all three trainings sessions is quite high. This motion can be supported by the increased number of stakeholders who would like to be informed about the following sessions. Hence, in the first training session, there should be a moment to reflect on how to adapt the next sessions to increase the relevance and value - which can also be seen as an action to inform about the next sessions.

Targeted communication, snowball outreach, and continuous dissemination through social media

Additionally, targeted communication strategies are essential to refine outreach methods and clearly convey the value proposition of BUILD activities created in Task 3.1. These steps include implementing engagement campaigns that showcase the tangible benefits of participation. Building on varying stakeholder preferences and brought value, the BUILD project can also consider the snowballing method for attracting participants for trainings following the first one. Lastly, the BUILD consortium will continue using the survey to engage additional stakeholders through social media channels, with the aim to expand the trainees also beyond the BUILD consortium's initial network. The social media communication regarding the trainings and the use of the engagement survey are activities that will be carried on until the time of the trainings, happening in March. This aligns with the final aim to have a targeted and interested audience.

5 Annexes

5.1 Survey invitation email

Dear innovation Suppliers, Procurers, and Enthusiasts,

We hope this message finds you well. You are receiving this email because one of the [BUILD](#) consortium partners thought that our future actions are valuable for you. If you wish to be left out of future engagements, please let us know. We are committed to ensuring that our engagements and communications align with your interests and preferences. To achieve this, we kindly request your participation in a brief survey designed to gather insights into your specific areas of interest and participation.

Survey Link (5 min.): [Insert Survey Link]

We would like to assure you that the email addresses we have used to reach out to you were obtained through a comprehensive scouting and mapping exercise conducted during the formation of the BUILD Consortium. Each partner organization within the consortium contributed to this process, which has allowed us to assemble a diverse and dynamic group of stakeholders.

For your reference, the members of the BUILD Consortium are:

[PEDAL](#)

[City of Rotterdam](#)

[CIVITTA](#)

[Valonia](#)

[City of Turku](#)

[Tartu City](#)

What is the BUILD project

As a quick reminder, the BUILD project is a two-year-long Coordination and Support Action, funded by the Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No. 101070745. Our primary objective is to support the demand for innovative goods and services in Europe by promoting sustainable innovation through public procurement. We aim to enhance the capacity of cities in innovation procurement by encouraging cooperation, knowledge sharing among public buyers, fostering innovation skills within these entities, and forging connections with research and innovation projects.

Your input in this survey will be instrumental in steering the direction of our consortium's activities and ensuring that they align with your expectations and interests. We highly value your participation and feedback, and we look forward to working collaboratively with you to achieve our shared goals.

Please take a moment to complete the survey by [Insert Deadline], and feel free to reach out if you have any questions or require further information.

Thank you for your continued support and involvement in the BUILD project.

Best regards,

5.2 Survey

BUILD Stakeholder Interest and Commitment

Dear innovation Suppliers, Procurers, and Enthusiasts,

We hope this message finds you well. You are receiving this email because one of the BUILD consortium partners thought that our future actions are valuable for you. If you wish to be left out of future engagements, please let us know. We are committed to ensuring that our engagements and communications align with your interests and preferences. To achieve this, we kindly request your participation in a brief survey designed to gather insights into your specific areas of interest and participation.

Our actions:

Capacity building trainings | Innovative procurement training sessions (one in Finland, Estonia, Slovakia, and The Netherlands) and a webinar (in English) are held in early spring of 2024. These half-day sessions are directed to cities motivated in procuring innovations and seeking best practices and useful tools in procurement. How to identify the potential of innovations? How other cities are approaching the innovative procurement? What are the different ways to reach the innovative goal? The trainings are build around discussion and best practices from various European countries. The webinar will be saved and it is available to watch freely.

Newsletter | In our newsletter we inform interested parties about progress made in the BUILD project, as well as share interesting news in the innovation procurement sphere.

Best,

[PEDAL](#)

[City of Rotterdam](#)

[CIVITTA](#)

[Valonia](#)

[City of Turku](#)

[Tartu City](#)

*** Indicates required question**

1. Organization name *

2. Please indicate your interest/commitment

Mark only one oval per row.

	I would like to stop being informed about this action	I would like to remain informed about this action	I would be interested in participating in this action
--	---	---	---

**Training 1:
How to identify the potential of innovations?**

<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

**Training 2:
How other cities are approaching the innovative procurement?**

<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

**Training 3:
What are the different ways to reach the innovative goal?**

<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Newsletter

<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------